

Questionnaire for the assessment of the willingness to pay for cultural-tourist ecosystem services

Introduction

The OG conducted an experimental analysis on the Monte Nerone area to evaluate the willingness to pay for the implementation of tourist-recreational services. The study area is located in the Marche Apennines, 60 km from the coast (a very touristic area), it's easily accessible and has a good road network.

The object of the research was to assess the value of the ecosystem services provided by the forest. The data collection was done through a questionnaire to the visitors, preceded by a brief description of the area attempting to inform visitors of its cultural, architectural and environmental, naturalistic and landscape values.

The questionnaire asked for biographical information, educational qualification, average income bracket, frequency of visit, and an evaluation of the main ecosystem services the area was able to provide (providing a grid of ecosystem services characterising the area as support for the answer).

The evaluation was carried out with a double key, on the one hand assessing the evaluation of the importance of the various ecosystem services for the users (e.g. the landscape, biodiversity, etc., with answer scores of 1-7), and on the other asking how the Nerone area responded according to their perception. These two parameters were considered as fundamental to determine their willingness to pay. In the end, participants were asked to survey express their interest and their willingness to pay for a parking space (assessment per vehicle not per person, per day). The money collected would be reinvested in the area to improve services and maintain the area.

Lessons learned

After the data analysis, a willingness to pay 7/8 euros was estimated. Most visitors are willing to pay for an access point with information and toilets and then go on an excursion. There was no ostracism only very few answers the environment belongs to everyone and they are not willing to pay.

No real implementation has followed so far. Difficulties in data collection (number of questionnaires about 90 completed, some filled in poorly, not usable). The thesis collector who collected the data took advantage of the possibility of collecting the information at events, but in general it is very difficult to find people. An attempt was made to collect data on Facebook but they were not found to be reliable. The people interviewed were very willing to answer, but these questionnaires are often too long for people who were passing by on holiday.

It is also difficult to balance between the level of detail one would like to achieve and the immediacy of the answers. If you want very large samples and detailed information, the period is very long.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.innovaturale.it/pei-agri/gruppi-operativi/bancadati-go-pei/biodiversita-e-servizi-ecosistemici-foreste-e-territorio>

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